

Polarographic Study of the Reaction Between Sodium Tungstate and Sodium Adipate

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Polarographic investigation of the reaction between sodium tungstate and sodium adipate in the presence of phosphoric acid-potassium chloride supporting electrolyte establishes a 1:1 complex with formation constant 5.91×10^{-8} mole per litre.

THE polarographic studies of tungsten (VI) have shown that in 7.3M phosphoric acid the metal is reduced to +5 state with a half-wave potential of -0.59 volts against S.C.E.^{1,2}. The present work deals with the polarographic investigation of the complex forming reaction between sodium tungstate and sodium adipate in phosphoric acid-potassium chloride supporting electrolyte. The p^H -metric, conductometric and spectrophotometric studies of the reaction have already established the formation of a 1 : 1 complex³. The well known polarographic technique for the investigation of complex compounds has been applied to confirm these results. The experimental details have been included in an earlier communication⁴. The adipic acid complexes of lead^{5,6} and cadmium⁷ have already been polarographically investigated.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. A freshly prepared gelatin solution (0.01%) was used as maxima suppressor. Purified hydrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. Doubly distilled mercury was used as DME. Polarographic

grams were obtained on an automatic Tinslay pen-recording polarograph. A Phillips p^H -meter, provided with a combined glass-calomel electrode was used for p^H measurements. Other conditions of the experiments have been shown in the Tables.

CONDITIONS FOR OBTAINING THE POLAROGRAMS : DAMPING 4, SENSITIVITY 5, DROP TIME 3 SEC/DROP

TABLE I
 $p^H = 6.35$

No.	Concentration of ligand solution	Logarithm of ligand concentration	Half-wave potential	Change in half-wave potential
1.	0.0000M	0.0000	-1.000	-
2.	0.0050M	-2.3010	-0.995	-0.005
3.	0.0100M	-2.0000	-0.987	-0.013
4.	0.0150M	-1.8239	-0.980	-0.020
5.	0.0200M	-1.6980	-0.975	-0.025
6.	0.0250M	-1.6021	-0.970	-0.030
7.	0.0300M	-1.5229	-0.965	-0.035
8.	0.0350M	-1.4559	-0.962	-0.038

Fig. 1A

Discussion

In 1M potassium chloride and $7.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ phosphoric acid tungsten (VI) is reduced first to +5 and then to +3 state just like molybdenum (VI)⁸. In

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TABLE 2

pH = 6.40

No.	Concentration of ligand solution	Logarithm of ligand concentration	Half-wave potential	Change in half-wave potential
1.	0.0000M	0.0000	-1.000	-
2.	0.0025M	-2.6021	-0.997	-0.003
3.	0.0050M	-2.3010	-0.987	-0.013
4.	0.0075M	-2.1249	-0.980	-0.020
5.	0.0100M	-2.0000	-0.977	-0.023
6.	0.0125M	-1.9031	-0.975	-0.025
7.	0.0150M	-1.8239	-0.970	-0.030
8.	0.0175M	-1.7570	-0.965	-0.035

presence of dicarboxylic acids like oxalic acid and its homologues, molybdates and tungstates do not form complexes with phosphoric and acetic acids⁹. The

changes in the half-wave potential of tungsten with the changes of concentration of the sodium adipate solution therefore, confirm the formation of a complex with this ligand. The composition and the formation constant of the complex are 1 : 1 and 5.91×10^{-8} mole per litre, respectively. Figures 1A and 1B show the straight lines obtained by plotting $E_{1/2}$ against $\log_{10} C_x$.

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